

Ethidium Bromide Risks and Safe Handling: What You Need to Know

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1. Introduction

Ethidium bromide, a household name in biology, is a fluorescent stain used to visualize nucleic acids in electrophoresis. It binds to DNA and fluoresces with a reddish-brown colour under ultraviolet light, intensifying its glow almost 20-fold. Discovered in the early 20th century, ethidium bromide's precursor, phenanthridine, was noted for its medicinal potential due to its quinoline ring structure. In 1938, phenanthridine derivatives effectively targeted *Trypanosoma* parasites causing African animal trypanosomiasis. By 1952, chemical modifications led to the development of ethidium bromide, a more potent and less toxic trypanocidal drug. Manufactured as Ethidium® by Boots Pure Drug Co., Ltd., it remained the preferred treatment for cattle trypanosomiasis for decades. Interestingly, its ability to intercalate DNA base pairs made it invaluable in molecular research, a discovery credited to Piet Borst and Cees Aaij. Today, it remains a staple in molecular biology laboratories worldwide.

2. Properties of Ethidium Bromide

Ethidium bromide (EtBr), chemically known as 3,8-diamino-5-ethyl-6-phenylbromide, or 2,7-diamino-10-ethyl-9-phenanthridinium bromide, or 2,7-diamino-9-phenylphenanthridinium ethobromide, is a prominent orange-red cationic fluorescent dye extensively used for visualizing nucleic acids. Its popularity stems from two key physiochemical features. First, as an aromatic compound, EtBr produces a reddish-orange light with a maximum emission at 560 nm when excited with wavelength from 260 to 360 nm (UV range). Second, its structural similarity to DNA base pairs allows EtBr to interpolate into double-

stranded DNA molecule(dsDNA). Additionally, EtBr can detect single-stranded RNA (ssRNA) due to RNA's tendency to fold back on itself, creating local base pairing. Upon integration into ssRNA or dsDNA, EtBr transitions from a watery to a hydrophobic milieu, forcing it to shed water molecules. Since water slakes fluorescence, its removal significantly enhances EtBr's fluorescence intensity when excited using suitable wavelength. This unique combination of properties has made EtBr an indispensable tool in molecular biology for imaging nucleic acids.

Structure of Ethidium Bromide

(Source:National Center for Biotechnology Information (2024). PubChem Compound Summary for CID 14710, Ethidium bromide. Retrieved August 7, 2024 from <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Ethidium-bromide>.)

3. Risks Associated with Ethidium Bromide

Ethidium bromide (EtBr) has been the subject of significant scrutiny regarding its safety, but current evidence provides some reassurance. So far, ethidium bromide (EtBr) has been classified as a probable, possible, or

unconfirmed carcinogen by leading health organizations, including the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), the National Toxicology Program (NTP), and the Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA). While EtBr is suspected to be mutagenic, it rarely penetrates intact cell membranes or the live cells and exerts its mutagenic potential. Currently, experimental data lacks in conclusively suggesting that EtBr is mutagenic in humans, mice, or rats. In ruminants and other agricultural animals, it was employed as veterinary drug at concentrations much loftier than those used in biological laboratories, with no apparent adverse effects. Furthermore, Ethidium Bromide (EtBr) is not directly Ames-positive; its mutagenic potential emerges only after it is metabolized by enzymes. This suggests that a derivative, rather than the original compound, could present a risk when ingested and processed by the liver. Nevertheless, this does not mean EtBr is entirely safe. It is prudent to regard it as a potential mutagenic and carcinogenic agent until more conclusive data are available. Therefore, strict precautionary measures should be followed, as an ounce of prevention is worth a pound of cure.

4. Safe Handling Practices

When handling ethidium bromide (EtBr), adhering to proper safety protocols is crucial. Nitrile gloves are generally sufficient to protect against dermal contamination, unlike natural rubber latex gloves, which do not provide an adequate barrier. Using a chemical fume hood to prepare stock solutions and handle EtBr is crucial to prevent aerosol inhalation, especially when working with dry powder or performing open or pressurized manipulations. Wearing nitrile gloves with a fully casing lab apron with wrist-length sleeves, along with goggles and face shields are recommended if splashes are possible; otherwise, usual laboratory safety glasses will suffice. Additionally, following the standard operating procedures for work practices, personal protective equipment and engineering controls, is necessary to minimize risk. It is also important to designate and restrict specific areas for using DNA stains. By upholding stringent laboratory protocols and following recommended safety measures, the risks linked to Ethidium Bromide can be effectively controlled, creating a safer work environment.

5. Disposal and Decontamination

Established practices for ethidium bromide waste management includes the following

A. Incineration

Agarose gels holding EtBr should be discarded in waste bins meant for hazardous materials, which are then incinerated at designated facilities. This method completely destroys most organic left-over and cuts of landfill volume. However, it's a costlier effort as it requires significant fuel, and raises concerns about air and water pollution.

B. Activated Charcoal

EtBr can be sieved effectively from solutions using commercially obtainable filters or destaining bags which contain activated charcoal as their ingredient and the obtained filtrate can be safely disposed of. These filters are efficient to bind about 174 μ g of EtBr and, once spent, they should be treated hazardous and send for incineration. This method is modest, effective, and fairly cheap, though it concentrates the chemical.

C. Chemical Degradation (Lunn and Sansone method)

EtBr-containing solutions are treated with 5% hypophosphorous acid and sodium nitrite of 0.5M concentration after diluting to 0.5 μ g/mL as a final concentration. After 20 hours of incubation with agitation, the blend is thus subjected for neutralized using sodium bicarbonate and drained away through the sink. These procedures are advised to be executed under fume hood, degrades over 99% of EtBr and produces non-mutagenic mixtures.

D. Amberlite XAD-16 Resin

EtBr can be efficiently eliminated using a resin, Amberlite XAD-16. This method is feasible and effective for decontamination.

In past decades, it was standard protocol to add sodium hypochlorite (bleach) to EtBr solutions prior to disposing them into drainage (Armour method). However, research by Lunn and Sansone (1987) demonstrated that this combination in fact emits more toxic byproducts. Additionally, using bleach for EtBr decontamination is inefficient, as it leaves behind approximately 20% of the original mutagenicity. Novel and other potentially promising methods for ethidium bromide degradation include phytoremediation, bacterial bioremediation, and phycoremediation using microalgae.

6. Alternatives for Ethidium Bromide

Several commercially available alternatives can substitute EtBr include Diamond™ Nucleic Acid Dye (Promega), SYBR® Safe and SYBR® Green (Thermo Fisher Scientific), RedSafe™ (Chembio), and GelRed™ and GelGreen™ (Biotium). Nevertheless, a genuine issue is that, misplaced and uninformed fears about Ethidium Bromide can sometimes result in the implementation of solutions that could be more dangerous than the substance itself. For instance, alternatives which are marketed as harmless substitutes for EtBr are not always genuinely safer. SYBR Safe, for example, was found to be more lethal than EtBr to bacterial cultures employed in mutagenicity tests, showing toxicity at concentrations as minimal as 1 microgram/ml, while EtBr showed no toxicity until 250 micrograms/ml. This increased toxicity is attributed to the higher permeability of living cells to SYBR Safe compared to EtBr. Interestingly, the Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS) for SYBR Safe documented LD50 for rats to be >5g/kg, which is higher than EtBr's LD50 of 1.5g/kg. Nonetheless, since both these LD50 values are significantly higher than the concentrations used in routine lab practices, the toxicity of gel staining solutions is considered trivial. Additionally, methylene blue and crystal violet dyes can be also thought as alternatives to EtBr, albeit with certain limitations. Other alternatives for visualizing DNA include DAPI, Propidium iodide, and Hoechst dye etc., but their use is less common and limited compared to ethidium bromide in visualization of nucleic acid in agarose gel.

7. Conclusion

Ethidium bromide (EtBr) has been a cornerstone in molecular biology for picturing nucleic acids, despite concerns about its safety. While there are effective disposal methods like incineration, activated charcoal, chemical degradation, and Amberlite™ XAD-16™ resin, the irrational fear of EtBr has led to the adoption of alternatives that may not be safer. It's crucial to remain informed and cautious about these substitutes, understanding that perceived safety does not always equate to actual safety. By being vigilant and not falling for misleading claims, we can ensure safe and effective laboratory practices.

References

- Lalchhandama, K., 2016. The making of modern biotechnology: how ethidium bromide made fame. *Scientific Visualization*, 16, pp.27-36.
- Gandhi, V.P., Kesari, K.K. and Kumar, A., 2022. The identification of ethidium bromide-degrading bacteria from laboratory gel electrophoresis waste. *BioTech*, 11(1), p.4.
- <https://bitesizebio.com/95/ethidium-bromide-a-reality-check/>
- <https://policies.unc.edu/TDClient/2833/Portal/Share/d/FileOpen?AttachmentID=12a4e81b-827b-483f-82dc-b96cd1a466e9&ItemID=132070&ItemComponent=26&IsInline=-1>
- <https://www.science.org/content/blog-post/myth-ethidium-bromide>

